

1 **Thioredoxin family activation in homeostasis loss.**

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6 Major thioredoxin family homeostasis effectors activated across cellular context included *Txnip* as well as
7 *Txnrd1* and *Txnrd2*. Other homeostasis effectors of the thioredoxin family found to be activated during
8 acute loss of homeostasis included Txndc5, Txndc11, Txndc16 and Txndc17. While some of these
9 molecules appeared to signal a shift or large change in homeostasis in the cell, others appeared to play a
10 more active role in goal-oriented management of changes in the cell that were themselves associated with
11 loss in homeostasis. Cells depleted of TXNIP displayed reciprocal activation of metallothionein stress
12 response gene *MT2A*, and this activation was among the most significant changes resulting from specific
13 loss of homeostasis effector TXNIP. For the thioredoxin family, the major functional consequence the
14 genes when serving as effectors influenced was protein folding and entropy in cellular homeostasis,
15 supporting the lowest energy state by providing optimal redox conditions in the cell for protein folding.

16 Citations

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